

Analysis of Armed Conflict and Peace Mission of Bosnia– Herzegovina through the Concept of Arm Conflict and Peace Mission (ACPM)

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ABSTRACT :The armed conflict of Bosnia-Herzegovina is one of the frightening events for Muslims in the world where there is a massacre that gets a bad response by many people. The armed conflict occurred from 1992 to 1995 which was included in the ethnic conflict. The region of Bosnia-Herzegovina has long had ethnic and religious diversity. Each of these ethnic groups has a political forum that forms a coalition in the government of Bosnia-Herzegovina. Geographically, Bosnia has a strategic location in the context of economic and political activities so that the kingdoms around Bosnia were involved in three major events that triggered the outbreak of World War I. The purpose of this study is to analyze the long conflict of Bosnia-Herzegovina through the concept of armed conflict and peacekeeping missions. The research method that will be used in this study uses descriptive qualitative research methods with a literature review approach based on library sources on data searches. Usually, the conflict can be resolved if both parties can lower their ego by prioritizing overall welfare, but human nature is to prioritize personal interests and those who dominate.

KEYWORDS –Bosnia-Herzegovina, Conflict, Ethnic, Peace Mission, Arm Conflict

I.INTRODUCTION

The armed conflict of Bosnia-Herzegovina is one of the frightening events for Muslims in the world where there is a massacre that gets a bad response by many people. The armed conflict occurred from 1992 to 1995 which was included in the ethnic conflict. The collapse of Yugoslavia that occurred in 1991 was initiated by the Bosnian war. After the collapse of Yugoslavia, the lower countries such as Croatia, Slovenia, Macedonia, and Bosnia became political and economic life that lost its way. In the end, these countries proclaimed themselves as free and independent countries. However, the declaration of independence made Serbia not accept it. Serbia rejected the proclamation because it wanted to keep a unitary state in the Balkans as part of the existence of a Yugoslav state. In its development, Serbia's desire led to armed conflict in Bosnia(Adi, 2018).

The region of Bosnia-Herzegovina is ethnically and religiously diverse. There are three types of diversity, namely the first is Bosnian, the second is Serb which is also called Ethnic Serb, and the last is Croatian (Ethnic Croatia). Bosnia-Herzegovina in 1991 separated from Yugoslavia. The existence of a political platform owned by these ethnic groups allows them to form a coalition with the government of Bosnia-Herzegovina. There are 99.7 percent in an area of Bosnia-Herzegovina whose ethnic majority is Serb, choosing Bosnia-Herzegovina to become a sovereign State (Firman, 2020).

Internationally, Bosnia-Herzegovina was recognized as an independent country by the European Community on April 6, 1992. Bosnia's population is predominantly Muslim, accounting for 45% of the total population of Bosnia. About 31% of orthodox Christians are of Serbian descent. Geographically, Bosnia has a strategic position in the context of economic and political activities so that the Bosnian kingdom is constantly fighting for power and competing for hegemony. During the reign of the Austro-Hungarian kingdom, Bosnia

was involved in three major events that sparked the outbreak of World War I. After World War I, Bosnia was divided into parts of Serbian-controlled territory. until 1929 and part of the Serbian-dominated federation until 1992(Rivaldy, Madjid, & Legowo, 2021).

Refendum that existed on March 1, 1992 with the content of Bosnia-Herzegovina as a sovereign state. Recognition of the proclamation on May 22, 1992 is an acknowledgment obtained from the international world which was accompanied by the entry into a member of the United Nations. The major cities of Bosnia in mid-1992 were attacked by ethnic Serbs with the aim of genocidal efforts against the people of the season in Bosnia. International security organizations, namely the United Nations and NATO, took part in overcoming the Bosnian war. Ethnic Serbs were attacked by air that lasted from August to September 1995 by the United Nations and NATO (Prabowo, 2020).

It can be said that the war that took place in Bosnia was a series of wars that had very complex problems and were related to racism that led to genocide. It can be seen in the previous paragraph, the Bosnian war got worse and prompted many parties to immediately resolve the war that was happening in Bosnia. Because of this very complex conflict, the Dayton Agreement was born. The Dayton Agreement is an agreement that aims to end one of the series of conflicts in the Yugoslav conflict, namely the Bosnian war. The agreement was approved at Wright Patterson Air Base in Dayton, Ohio. The meeting before this agreement was signed was held from November 1 to 2, 1995 and was attended by many key figures in the Bosnian war, such as Serbian President Slobodan Milosevic, Croatian President Franjo Tudman, Bosnian president Alija Izetbegovic, US chief negotiator Richard Holbrooke, and General Wesley. Clark. The Dayton Agreement was officially signed by the parties in Paris, France on December 14, 1995. Then with the Dayton agreement, it also marked the end of the Bosnian War. However, the Dayton Agreement did not necessarily bring the Yugoslav conflict to an end, because the Yugoslav conflict really ended in 2003 (Arjanto, 2021).

From the background that has been described by the researcher, the formulation of the problem that will be analyzed by the researcher is formulated as follows:

- a. What are the types, sources, and actors of the armed conflict in Bosnia?
- b. What is the solution to resolve the conflict through a peace mission?

II. RESEARCH METHODS

This research uses descriptive qualitative research method. Research design is a step that must be arranged systematically, effectively, and efficiently to be able to answer questions or suspected problems presented in a study. Literature review is an approach in answering this research question. The literature review approach is an approach that is based on library sources on data searches from books, articles, journals, and so on regarding a topic to be discussed which ultimately results in a single article on a particular topic (Setiawan & Muhid, 2021). According to Sukmadinata (2011), descriptive qualitative research is intended to describe and describe existing phenomena, meaning that these phenomena can be in the form of no regulation or based on human settings by looking at the quality, characteristics, and interests between what is being done.(Zulkhairi, Arneliwati, & Nurchayati, 2018).

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Result

Conflict Type

Article 2 in International Humanitarian Law contains arrangements for international armed conflicts, where the situation regulated in the article is regarding armed conflicts that take place between two countries. The state is the content of the Geneva Conventions in which the party in determining the status of the conflict is since the conflict occurs between the members (Lia, 2019).

The Serbia-Herzegovina armed conflict is an international armed conflict. It is said to be an international armed conflict because the conflict occurs between one country and another. From what has been

described by the researcher in the background, the armed conflict involved several camps such as Bosnia and the federation of Yugoslavia.

Source of Conflict

The source of conflict is how the conflict begins and becomes a prolonged conflict. From what has been described in the background, according to the researcher, there are three causes of the Serbia-Herzegovina armed conflict, namely:

- a. Bosnia and Serbia have diversity in many ways, including culture, religion, and ethnicity
- b. Bosnia does not have the power compared to Serbia in terms of social, economic, and political in Bosnian society
- c. Economic activities in the Bosnia region are good and strategic.

Conflict Actor

There are two actors who became several conflict camps that contributed to the prolonged conflict. In the area of Bosnia-Herzegovina there are three ethnicities, namely Bosniak, the two Serbs who are also called Ethnic Serbs, and the last one is Kroat (Ethnic Croatia). Bosnia-Herzegovina in 1991 separated from Yugoslavia. Each ethnic group has a political coalition that forms a coalition in the government (winner of the 1990 general election) of Bosnia-Herzegovina. However, since 1991, the coalition began to crumble, and each ethnic group chose to fight for their own interests. The referendum was held from February 29 to March 1, 1992. A total of 99.7 percent of voters wanted Bosnia-Herzegovina to declare independence two days later. On April 6, 1992, international recognition emerged, and the country became a member of the United Nations on May 22, 1992. It's just that Bosnians of Serb ethnicity rejected this independence. In the referendum, almost no Serb voted. Bosnian Serb paramilitary troops attacked the city of Sarajevo, and Serb troops from the Yugoslav army immediately intervened on their side. Cities with large Bosniak populations such as Zvornik, Foca, and Visegrad became the main targets of the joint forces' attacks. The incident is commonly described as an attempt to cleanse the Bosniak by Serbs. About six weeks after the offensive began, the invading forces had captured about two-thirds of Bosnia (Firman, 2020).

3.2 Discussion

Usually, international armed conflicts occur when parties promise not to carry out international agreements that have been made, there is a struggle for economic, security and political influence, and there is an intervention against the sovereignty of other countries. After being observed by researchers, the Serbia-Herzegovina armed conflict occurred because of differences in beliefs, ethnicity, and dominance in the economy, social and politics. At that time, the Serbs carried out indiscriminate attacks on Bosnia. The indiscriminate opposition to the state declaring its independence was an attempt to prevent the state from liberating itself. The brutality that occurred in Bosnia was caused by the majority Muslim population of Bosnia. The armed conflict that started as an ethnic conflict then escalated into a religious conflict. This caused a reaction from other Islamic countries. The conflict that occurred was one of the social conflicts that occurred for a long time and in historical records a major conflict based on races.

Peace is the goal of this, various efforts are always carried out, for example, through many negotiations. There have been several attempts to reconcile the armed conflict (Masnun, 2017). These efforts include:

1. UN Call

The United Nations tried to mediate against the Bosnian war with Serbia by sending an envoy named Yasuki Asaki. The warning to withdraw the Serbian army in Bosnia, which was followed by the

imposition of sanctions on Serbia for the cruel massacre of Serbs, were efforts to end the conflict as soon as possible.

2. Action of G-7 countries

The G-7 countries are Canada, France, Germany, Italy, Japan, the United Kingdom, and the United States. The European Union also represents the G-7. Where the country is a major developed economic country. The G-7 countries are trying to pressure Serbia to stop military invasion of Croatia, which is expected to find a peaceful solution to the problem without war, this was stated in the negotiations in Texas, United States.

3. NATO's Role

NATO in terms of the Bosnian War is a war that requires it to go directly to the field. NATO action focuses on peacemaking (Fakhriansyah, 2021). Sending NATO troops in the Bosnian war is to create an area free from the violence of the Serbian army. Sanctions for Serbia for its aggression by NATO is by air strikes on Serbian troops.

4. Indonesia's Role

The chairman of the Non-Aligned Movement, namely Indonesia at that time during the Suharto era, contributed to the problems that occurred. President Suharto argued that if the conflict could be resolved, it must use negotiation efforts. The Garuda XIV contingent containing troops consisting of 25 ABRI officers was assigned to Yugoslavia as an act of participating in conflict resolution efforts.

5. Dayton Negotiations in the United States

This negotiation is the end of a prolonged conflict that occurred here under the supervision of NATO and the United States, both parties are willing to resolve the problem by negotiating. Negotiations at Dayton were held on November 1, 1995, in which the Bosnians were represented by Alisa Izet Begovic and Franco, while Slobodan represented Serbia. The Dayton negotiations became the backdrop for the settlement agreement signed in France on November 14, 1995.

IV. CONCLUSION

Armed conflicts that occur nationally and internationally caused by ethnic and religious differences often occur and have existed since ancient times. However, sometimes there are conflicts that can be resolved with the help of outsiders or not. But there are also conflicts that escalated and continue to this day.

Usually, the conflict can be resolved if both parties can lower their egos by not prioritizing their beliefs and preferring to prioritize the welfare of both parties. However, as stated in the Human Needs theory put forward by Maslow, the basic nature of humans is that the interests of each party dominate. This makes it difficult for conflicts to be resolved immediately.

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